

Oiconomy Pricing - Real price of cocoa liquor from single origin beans, Sierra Leone

Company	Tradin Organic
Location	Amsterdam, The Netherlands
Product	1 ton of cocoa liquor
Currency	Euro
Oiconomy Assessment	<u>Oiconomy Sustainability Assessment Tool v2.04</u>
Timeframe	Data from 2021

Case description

Tradin Organic is a Dutch B2B company, which sources, distributes, and processes organic food ingredients to the international food market. Within its wide product portfolio, the case is single origin, organic cocoa liquor, from cocoa beans which are cultivated by smallholder farmers, located in Sierra Leone. The cocoa beans are bought in from the smallholder farmers and processed in a factory owned by Tradin Organic and stationed in The Netherlands. Tradin Organic has several impact programs aimed at to improving the environmental and social sustainability of the cocoa supply chain but has not yet quantified the externalities associated with the product.

Scope of assessment:

Figure 1: Scope of assessment: supply chain actors and outputs

The supply-chain of 1 ton of cocoa liquor was traced back by including 80% of the purchased value. This identified the most relevant supply- chains and actors: **the cocoa farmers, the corporate entity on location (Sierra Leone), the corporate trader (Netherlands) and the liquor producer** (Figure 1).

The **cocoa beans** are cultivated in Sierra Leone by the smallholder farmers and sold to the corporate entity on location, Tradin Sierra Leone (SL). Tradin SL further sells it to the corporate trader in The Netherlands (Tradin Cocoa; Tradin Organic), which delivers it to the liquor producing facility in The Netherlands. This facility processes the cocoa beans into cocoa liquor and sells it back to the trader (Tradin Cocoa; Tradin Organic), which then sells the end product to the market (producer of final chocolate products). As the product is organic certified, no pesticides or agro-chemicals are used in its cultivation and/or processing.

Total results

Hidden costs show what impact the product has on planet, people and prosperity, that are currently not reflected in the prices charged for the goods along the value chain. The impact can be negative or positive. The negative costs are based on costs of prevention, meaning the costs necessary to eliminate the negative impact. The total hidden costs of 1 ton of cocoa liquor are **€ 427,22** (Figure 2). The average sales price of 1 ton of cocoa liquor is **€ 4320,00** meaning the hidden costs are adding **10%** onto the sales price. Figure 3 displays the negative hidden costs per supply-chain partner.

Figure 2: The main negative hidden costs of 1 ton of cocoa liquor

Figure 3: Negative hidden cost per supply-chain partner

The main negative hidden costs come from the category **Pollution & Climate**, connected to the CO₂ emissions of cocoa farming. Despite the lack of artificial fertilizers and agro-chemicals used, it still results in **€ 155,49** costs for the farmers. Furthermore, CO₂ emissions from the processing of cocoa beans into liquor is also present, resulting in the total cost of **€ 34,68** for the producer. Lastly, pollution costs concerning the transport of beans from Sierra Leone to The Netherlands, and then further to the international market, are also prominent, which results in **€ 35,84** and **€ 69,42** for Tradin Sierra Leone and Tradin Netherlands, respectively.

The second and third biggest cost categories are **Waste & Disposal** and **Labour**. Concerning the former, most costs, i.e., **€ 55,04**, are related to the residual steams in the processing facility. Regarding the latter, labor costs are connected to the risk of child labor in the cocoa farms, as well as the lack of investments on health insurance plans, resulting in **€ 17,86** costs for the farmers, but also **€ 15,98** related to inequality ratio between the likely highest and lowest paid salary for Tradin Netherlands.

Despite these hidden negative costs, this assessment also demonstrated the absence of negative impacts on various aspects, such as **Depletion of resources, Biodiversity & Land Degradation** and **Land Occupation**. These results are supported by several factors, such as minimum input needed for harvesting of cocoa beans, including the lack of artificial fertilizers, agro-chemicals and irrigation, as well as Tradin Organic's investments on agroforestry programs and the promotion of sustainable agriculture practices, focused on soil health and improvement. Additionally, under **Labour**, the assessment also shows that concerning **fair wages**, farmers get fairly remunerated for their products.

Figure 4: Photo of cocoa fruits

Positive costs

Figure 5: Positive costs of 1 ton of cocoa liquor

Besides negative hidden costs, positive costs were also calculated (Figure 5). Positive costs are based on actual company spending, benefitting others than the ones involved in the transaction. **Positive costs** of € 51,14 were found, mostly spent by Tradin Sierra Leone and Tradin Netherlands. Highlights of CSR programs include those focused on improving farmer communities' food security (under the category **Human health & Social conditions**), monitoring and addressing the root causes of child labor (under the category of **Labor**), promoting sustainable and regenerative agricultural practices and investing on farmers' technical skills, as well as agroforestry programs (under the category of **Pollution & Climate, Biodiversity & Land degradation**).

Data specificity

Hidden costs are calculated as the sum of the quantity of an issue (performance data), and the costs to prevent the issue (prevention costs). Both performance data and prevention costs can be company-specific or generic database-sourced.

Performance data are measuring the sustainability performance of companies (e.g. kWh used). All value chain actors were able to complete the assessment using mainly company-specific data.

Prevention costs are data on the costs of sustainability mitigation measures (e.g. investing in solar panels). None of the value-chain partners were able to provide much company-specific prevention costs, as it takes time to make investment proposals to mitigate the impact. This should be a focus when the assessment is repeated. So, all prevention costs were calculated by used default value

Company reflection

"Despite the complexity of the process, the results are practical and lead to a better understanding of where further corporate sustainability investments are needed. The required collaboration and transparency has given us a better perspective of the complexity of our value chains. The Oiconomy Tool has definitely helped us, although its user-friendliness needs improvement."

"Within Tradin Organic the results get shared with the management and will be made available to all staff, also in Sierra Leone. The responsible teams will determine interventions based on the results."

- Sustainability Manager

Utrecht University thanks Tradin Organic for their transparency and cooperation. More information is available online on the explanation of the Oiconomy Pricing [method and its principles](#), the Oiconomy Pricing [tool](#), and [examples of companies applying the method](#). For contact, please reach out to oiconomy@uu.nl

Disclaimer: this assessment was based on company data, but not independently verified.

Authors: Anne Floor van Dalfsen, Beatriz Daim, Pim R. Croes, Walter J.V. Vermeulen, Anna Walker

Date of publication: 11-09-2023

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.8296465